

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/MsABINLAL H bearing USN6SU19RC001 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Respiratory therapy programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/MsASHWATHI KUMAR K bearing USN6SU19RC002 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Respiratory therapy programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms FATHIMA FIDA bearing USN6SU19RC003 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Respiratory therapy programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms FATHIMATH NEEHA SHERIN bearing USN6SU19RC004 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre, Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Respiratory therapy programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/MsHAMEEMA BASHEER bearing USN6SU19RC005 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Respiratory therapy programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsHEPHZIBA RAJAN bearing USN6SU19RC006 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Respiratory therapy programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms IRISHI RAJ ABHILASH bearing USN6SU19RC007 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre, Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Respiratory therapy programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms LIBIN BABY N bearing USN6SU19RC008 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Respiratory therapy programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms MOHAMED BASITH bearing USN6SU19RC009 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre, Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Respiratory therapy programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms MOHAMED SHAHIN bearing USN6SU19RC010 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre, Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Respiratory therapy programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms MUHAMMED ASHIK T M bearing USN6SU19RC011 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre, Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Respiratory therapy programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsNEENA SAJAN bearing USN6SU19RC012 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Respiratory therapy programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsNEENU PRAKASH bearing USN6SU19RC013 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Respiratory therapy programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms NIKHIL T BABU bearing USN6SU19RC014 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre, Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Respiratory therapy programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms PRINCE JOSEPH bearing USN6SU19RC015 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre, Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Respiratory therapy programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/MsSHILFAS K K bearing USN6SU19RC016 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Respiratory therapy programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsSHIYAD T bearing USN6SU19RC017 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Respiratory therapy programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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